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Human Resource Planning Practices And Sustainability Of Cosmetic Retail Firms In Anambra State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the human resource planning practices and sustainability of cosmetic retail firms in Anambra State. The researcher developed two objectives so as to; Determine how Training influence economic sustainability of cosmetics retail firms in Anambra State; Identify how talent acquisition influence economic sustainability of cosmetics retail firms in Anambra State. Data were generated through primary and secondary sources. The method for data collection was questionnaire which was administered randomly among the staff of the cosmetic firms in Anambra state. The population of the study was five hundred and eighty-seven (587), the sample size of the study was the same as the population, While five hundred and seventy-five (577) were retrieved. The hypotheses were tested using correlation analysis method at 0.05% level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that, Training has significant relationship on economic sustainability of cosmetics retail firms in Anambra State ($r=580$ $p=0.00$) Talent acquisition has significant relationship on economic sustainability of cosmetics retail firms in Anambra State ($r=690$ $p=0.00$). The study recommended that; Employees should be trained according to the present content of the environment. Therefore, seminars/ workshop should be regularly organized by the management in order to update the employee knowledge; Cosmetics retail firms should ensure the protection of their talent acquired within the organization so as to gain a better employee creativity and better performance

Keywords: human resource planning practices, sustainability, cosmetic retail, Training, talent acquisition

1.1 INTRODUCTION

In recognition of the importance of Human resource planning practices, the United National Economic Commission for Africa (1991) has described Human resource planning as the knowledge, skills, attitudes, physical and managerial effort required to manipulate resource, technology, land and material to produce goods and services for human consumption. In the same vein, (Igbinoba Marvin & Najimu (2022) suggested that at the macro-level, Human resource planning practices is about three key capacities namely; the capacity to develop talents, the capacity to deploy talents, and the capacity to draw talents from elsewhere. Collectively, these three capacities formed the backbone of any country's human capital competitiveness. In a collaborative view, (Edeh & Dialoke (2020) sees Human resource planning practices as the most important element of success in business today. According to him, developing human resource requires creating and cultivating environment in which human beings can rapidly learn and apply new ideas, competencies, skills, behaviours and attitudes. It could therefore, be deduced that

human capital represents the stock of competencies, knowledge, habits, social and personality attributes, so as to produce economic value (Atueyi, & Mbanefo 2025).

Hamza Othman, Gardi, Sorguli, Aziz, Ahmed, Sabir, & Ismael, Ali, & Anwar, (2021) explains that Human resource planning practices signifies building a, critical mass of human capital base and providing an enabling environment for everyone to participate fully in national development efforts. He further states that developing the Human resource planning practices involves providing opportunities for the citizens to develop their fullest potentials. It can be seen that Human resource planning practices is the key to the development of any country. It is the process of ensuring that a country has adequate number of qualified persons available at the proper times to drive her developmental efforts. Thus, countries and organizations are saddled with the task of developing their human capital. It is evident that this task must be carried out conscientiously and painstakingly if they hope to survive in the current dynamic global and competitive environment (Nwangwu, Ohanyere, Nwangwu, & Atueyi, 2025).

The emphasis on human resource in organizations reflects the view that market value depends less on tangible resource but rather on intangible ones particularly human resource. Recruiting and retaining the best employees are definitely not enough. The present study ‘human resource planning practices and sustainability of cosmetics industry in Anambra State’ finds motivation by adding to the empirical database of the human resource planning practices and organizational sustainability link as it affects the selected organizations (Ifechukwu-jacobs, & Atueyi, 2024).

Unpredictable market trends can pose significant challenges for human resource planning, as it becomes difficult to anticipate workforce needs and capabilities. This can result in misalignment between the skills and resource of the organization and the demands of the market, leading to talent shortages, missed opportunities, or overstaffing. To address this issue, organizations should adopt a flexible and adaptable approach to human resource planning, such as investing in employee development and cross-training, recruiting diverse talent pool, and utilizing data and analytics to anticipate market trends and workforce needs (Ifechukwu-Jacobs, Arinze, & Nwangwu, & Atueyi, 2025).

Resource constraints, whether financial, technological, or time-related, can also hinder effective human resource planning. Lack of budget or insufficient tools and systems can limit an organization’s ability to attract, train, and retain talent, ultimately impacting its performance and competitiveness. Organizations facing resource constraints should prioritize their human resource efforts based on their business goals and needs. They may also need to explore alternative approaches to talent management, such as outsourcing, automation, or talent sharing arrangements (Onya, Arinze, & Atueyi, 2025).

Employee turnover can be a significant issue in human resource planning, leading to increased recruitment and training costs, knowledge loss, and decreased productivity. High turnover rates may be indicative of underlying issues with the organization’s culture, compensation, or career development opportunities. To address employee turnover, organizations should focus on building a positive work environment, providing opportunities for professional growth and development, and offering competitive compensation and benefits packages. Retention strategies should also be tailored to specific employee segments, such as millennials or high-potential employees, to address their unique needs and motivations (Ohanyere Arinze, & Atueyi 2025).

Most of the workers are unskilled and they make use of outdated resource, equipment and methods of production. By implication, their marginal productivity is extremely low and this leads to low income, low savings, low investment and consequently low rate of resource formation. Overtime, the following issues relating to the concept have remained unresolved: Uneven distribution of skilled manpower, Misemployment of human resource planning in Nigeria, Poor reward system retarding the acquisition and development of human resource planning.

1.2 Objectives of the study

The broad objective of the study is to analyze the human resource planning practices and sustainability of cosmetics retail firms in Anambra State. The specific objectives are to:

- i. Determine how Training influences economic sustainability of cosmetics retail firms in Anambra State

- ii. Identify how talent acquisition influences economic sustainability of cosmetics retail firms in Anambra State

1.3 Research Questions

- i. How does Training influence economic sustainability of cosmetics retail firms in Anambra State?
- ii. In which way does talent acquisition influence economic sustainability of cosmetics retail firms in Anambra State?

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Conceptual Review

i Human Resource Planning (HRP)

Human resource planning (HRP) has been a major issue amongst scholars and practitioners in the field of human resource management quite apart from managers in other fields of studies. Human resource planning includes all activities that human resource managers adopt to forecast current and future workforce needs (Kurdi, Alshuridehb, & Afaishata, 2020). Digressing from Anwar, & Abdullah, (2021). argued that human resource planning is a process of anticipating as well as preparing for retiring workers exit and replace them with newcomers. In the same vein, Carnevale, & Hatak, (2020) contended that human resource planning refers to how human resource managers assess the current position of an organization's workforce with reference to what it tends to achieve in the future. Gardi, (2021) argued that human resource planning is the process through which management tries to provide information about the number of workers it has and the expected workforce it will require in the future. For Kurdi, Alshurideh, Salloum, Obeidat, & Al-were, (2020). HRP is a process of gathering and using relevant information to support decisions of human resource management on how to invest resource in manpower activities. Nondoh, Tsuma, Alala, & Onyango, 2020) submitted that human resource planning is the process for ensuring that the manpower requirements of an organization are identified and plans are made for satisfying those requirements. Obisi, Samuel, & Ilesanmi, (2020) viewed human resource planning as the process by which the management determines how the organization should move from its present manpower position to its desired position.

ii Economic Sustainability

Economic sustainability refers to practices designed to create the long-term economic development of a company or nation while also managing the environmental, social, and cultural aspect of its activities. It is about balancing economic growth and generating profit with the impact on the environment and people. There are three key areas of economic sustainability, namely: economic viability, environmental protection and social equity (Vineeth, 2020).

While it may seem like this pillar is focused on an organisation's ability to remain profitable throughout its lifetime, economic sustainability isn't just about money. An economically sustainable organisation is one that drives revenue and maintains long-term business growth without negatively impacting the community, environment, or health and wellbeing of its employees. Economic sustainability allows businesses to decipher where they can improve their sustainability measures and reduce their carbon footprint in order to adhere to new environmental regulations as well as attract new customers and investors (Younas, Farooq, Khalil-Ur-Rehman, & Zreen, (2018).. The traditional measure of the economic performance is the gross domestic product or GDP, which represents the total value of all goods and services produced by a nation during a given year. Other economic indicators include: Investment in public, Business and private assets, Social investment, Rate of inflation and Government borrowing and debts, Competitiveness/productivity and trade/export/imports etc.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on Gray and Herr's theory of Human Resource Management (HRM)

2.2.1 Human Resource Theory by Gray and Herr's theory (1998)

Gray and Herr's theory of Human Resource Management (HRM) argues that effective HRM practices can have a significant impact on organizational performance. According to their theory, effective HRM

requires a strategic alignment between these three components, with HRM philosophies guiding the development and implementation of HRM systems and practices. This strategic alignment, in turn, can lead to improved employee engagement, organizational performance, and competitive advantage.

HRM involves two key components:

1. Human resource management philosophy - This includes the beliefs and values held by an organization related to employees, their role, and their treatment.
2. Human resource management systems - These systems encompass the HR-related policies, procedures, and processes used by an organization, such as recruitment, training, and performance management.

Application of Gray and Herr's theory can be applied in various HRM practices and contexts, such as:

1. Talent Management: HRM philosophies can guide the development of talent management practices, such as recruitment, selection, and succession planning, to ensure that these practices align with the organization's beliefs and values, ultimately attracting, retaining, and developing talent that supports the organization's strategy.
2. Employee Engagement: HRM systems and practices can be designed to enhance employee engagement, such as by creating a positive work environment, offering competitive compensation and benefits, and providing opportunities for professional development.

The relevance of Gray and Herr's theory to HR practices

Enhanced Organizational Performance: Aligned HRM can lead to improved employee engagement, productivity, and overall organizational performance, as employees are more likely to be motivated and satisfied when their beliefs and values align with those of the organization.

Competitive Advantage: By ensuring that HRM practices align with organizational strategy and goals, organizations can gain a competitive advantage over their rivals by leveraging their human capital effectively.

Some common critiques include:

1. Limited Applicability: The theory may not be as applicable to non-Western, non-corporate organizations, as it assumes a Western, corporate-centric perspective on HRM.
2. Overly Strategic Focus: Critics argue that the theory overemphasizes the strategic role of HRM and does not adequately address the role of HRM in supporting day-to-day operations and addressing practical issues.

.3 Empirical Review

Edeh, & Dialoke, (2020) investigate the effect of human resource planning on the organizational performance of selected hotels in Nigeria. It is a cross-sectional survey research. A self-developed close-ended questionnaire was used to collect data from managers, supervisors, and front desk officers working in 15 selected hotels operating in Ebonyi state, Nigeria. Descriptive statistics were used to analyze participants' demographic characteristics while regression was used to analyze the hypotheses. The study found that human resource planning dimensions, namely, adequate funding, competence, age, and cultural background have a positive significant effect on organizational performance. The HR managers must focus on the financial capability of the firm as well as the age, competence, and cultural orientation of the prospective employees while making the HR planning.

Awolaja, (2023) examined the effect of HRM on employee performance of manufacturing company in Nigeria. Data for the study were obtained from a structured questionnaire administered among 2 sectors (consumer and industrial goods) of the manufacturing industries in Nigeria. For consumer goods, Unilever Nigeria Plc and Nestle Nigeria Plc. were selected while for industrial goods, Triple GEE and Company; and Dangote Cement Plc. were selected. Pearson product correlation and multiple regression analysis of ordinary least square were the estimation techniques employed. The results indicated that occupational health and safety, recruitment and selection and training and development exhibited a significant positive effect on the employees' performance of the manufacturing company in Nigeria.

Eze & Omena, (2023) re-examine the importance of human resource in Nigerian organisational development. The objectives of the study include to find ways to improve human resource to ensure development in Nigeria and to find the relationship between workforce and development. Hence, to achieve the goals of an organization, human resource management (HRM) must be properly addressed. The research work recommends that workers motivation to achieve organizational goal and development, management should always use the result of training for promotion and increment of remuneration packages and annual performance appraisal, and evaluation of workers should also be properly and equitably conducted.

Ubah, & Ibrahim, (2021). examines the effect human resource planning has on the performance of public sector organizations in Nigeria. The study adopted a cross-sectional survey research design with the collection of primary data using a questionnaire that was administered to 100 employees in the human resource department of the Ministry of Works and housing in Abuja, Nigeria. Correlation analysis using Pearson correlation was employed to determine the relationship between the variables and regression analysis was used to analyze the hypotheses with the aid of the IBM statistical package for social sciences. The result findings revealed that the multiple correlation coefficient indicates a strong correlation between the variables ($R= 0.779$). and that projected demand for workforce and recruitment and selection account for 60.7% of the total variation in organization performance. Of the two variables used, the recruitment and selection process account for the highest contribution to organization performance. Effective human resource planning in terms of projected demand for workforce and recruitment and selection will enable institutions to attract the right kind of people in the right numbers, improve employees' expertise, talents, and abilities, and keep them in the business.

Anozie, Chima & Onuoha, (2020). human resource management and organizational performance of nigerian firms human resource planning in an organization ensures that there is always qualified personnel at the right job at the right time in the short, medium and long term. Also given that the company have adequate manpower there is also need to have career development plans, successions plans and appropriate compensation plans to ensure that the company retains its good hands and avoid worker turnover or loss of key personnel to competitors. This underlines the function and importance of Human Resource Management. This study is a theoretical review of various empirical works in the area of the impact of human resource management on organizational performance of Nigeria firms. The methodology adopted was a detailed review of literature in same or related topics. Prominent articles in electronic resource and reputable online journalism the area of management and Human resource management were accessed. There was special focus on review of empirical studies of HRM and OP of Nigeria firms. All the reviewed empirical works tend to agree that there is a positive relationship between human resource management and organizational performance. Human resource management practices of training and career development, motivation showed significant positive contribution to organizational performance. Several issues and challenges to human resource management in Nigerian firms were highlighted and possible solutions were proffered.

Chioke, & Mbamalu, 2020) examined human resource planning and organizational performance: a philosophical approach. Organizations in the Nigerian context have suffered supply shortage and this has remained an ugly reoccurring decimal in the nation's Public Enterprises and Civil Service and one cannot therefore look askance at this trouble and wallow in the pretense that all is well with the sovereign entity wrongly called the giant of Africa. The persisting quagmire is the inability of organizations to attain the mission and purpose for which it stands for. Using secondary sources of data, the study was poised to ascertain and demonstrate how human resource planning affects the nation's organizational performance and thus relayed a dialectical correlation between human resource planning and organizational performance. As a way forward; human resource planning should be subjected to the rigors of HRP international best practices, civil service rules, morals, values and ethics of the profession. As its concluding remark, the study added that, human resource planning is a key factor for optimum organizational performance, growth and sustainable development of any formal organization and the nation at large.

Osazevbaru, Okwuise & Akpomiemie, (2023) examined the relationship between human resource planning and the organizational performance of telecom companies in Delta State. The objectives of the study were to; ascertain the relationship between workforce forecasting and organizational performance; determine the relationship between recruitment and selection and organizational performance; examine the relationship between employee training and development and organizational performance and determine the relationship between employee retention and organizational performance. The study employed a cross-sectional research design. A sample size of 169 was selected from the Human Resource executives of Telecom companies. Data collected through questionnaires were analyzed using descriptive statistics, correlation and multiple regressions. Results from the study revealed that there is a significant relationship between human resource planning (workforce forecasting, recruitment and selection, training and development and employee retention) and organizational performance.

METHODOLOGY

3.1: Research Design

This study employed survey research design, the reason for chosen it was because Survey research allows for collecting data from a large number of respondents, which can increase the generalizability and reliability of the results.

3.2: Sources of Data

The sources of data in this study comprises the primary and secondary.

Primary Data: These consist of all the data and information obtained personally from respondents through interviews and the use of questionnaire. They are primary in nature because they have not been published elsewhere.

3.3: Population of the Study.

This describes characteristics of the population of the staff. The population of interest comprised all the staff of cosmetics firms which is 587. The study used the entire population as the sample size because it is not up to 1000

s/n	Cosmetics firms	Address	Staff strength
1	Beta cosmetics manufacturing company	7 Umuoji Str, Obosi Anambra	98
2	Obimma chemical & cosmetics co. ltd	31, Venn Rd Onitsha, Anambra State, Anambra Lga City, Onitsha	97
3	Ekulo group of companies, Nigeria	J3, Ezichi Street, Niger Bridge Head, Onitsha	109
4	Kriswell cosmetics co. ltd	No 103, Nnamd Azikiwe road, parm site Awka Anambra state Nigeira, Nigeria	102
5	Kates Associated Industries Ltd	No 76 Niger Bridge Head Industrial Layout, Ogbaru,	109
6	Amex Soap & Detergents Manufacturers Ltd	1, Obiofia Nnewichi Nnewi , Nnewi , Anambra.	72
	Total		587

Sources: Human Resource Department of the Firms (2026)

3.4: Sampling Technique

The research employed stratified sampling. Stratified random sampling accords each of the respondents in the organization to be selected without bias.

3.5: Method of Data Collection.

The instrument used for data collection was questionnaire. The questionnaire consists of two sections, the section A is the respondent’s profile, while the section B is the general information. The questionnaire is designed using 5 point Likert scale that constructed according to the objectives of the study and oral interview was carried out to support the questionnaire.

3.6: Method of Data Analysis

Statistics such as frequency count and percentages table were used in the analysis of questions, while hypotheses were tested using correlation analysis. The hypotheses was assessed at 0.05 level of significance. Analysis were carried out with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS).

PRESENTATION ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

4.1 Response Rate

However, the number of questionnaire distributed was five hundred and ninety-two (587), whereas five hundred and seventy-seven (577) filled well and returned in good condition. The number of returned questionnaire was used for the analysis of the study.

Table 4.1: Respondents' Demographic Variables

4.1.1 Gender

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Male	451	75.5	78.2	78.2
Female	126	21.1	21.8	100.0
Total	577	96.6	100.0	

Source: Field Survey 2025

The above table reveals that the four hundred and fifty-one (451) of the respondents which represents 78.2 persons were male respondents, while one hundred and twenty-six (126) respondents which represent 21.8% were female respondents. By implication, male respondents were more than female respondents by 56.1 respondents in our selected population sample for this study. The implication of this is to enable us to know the number of female and male that successfully returned their questionnaire

4.1.2 Status

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Married	384	64.3	66.6	66.6
Single	193	32.3	33.4	100.0
Total	577	96.6	100.0	

Source: Field Survey 2025

In the table above, out of the five hundred and seventy-seven (577) respondents, three hundred and eighty-four (384) of the respondents were married, while one hundred and ninety-three (193) respondents which represent 33.4 percent are single. It is therefore glaring that the majority of the respondents are married as at the time of this study. Thus marital status table help us to know the number of single, and married, and respondents that answered the distributed questionnaire

4.1.3 Level of Education

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid WAEC/NECO	123	20.6	21.3	21.3
BSC/HND	177	29.6	30.7	52.0
MSC/MBA	198	33.2	34.3	86.3
PHD	79	13.2	13.7	100.0
Total	577	96.6	100.0	

Source: Field Survey 2025

The table above indicates that one hundred and twenty-three (123) respondents which representing 21.3% percent maintain to acquired WAEC OR NECO while 30.7% percent of the respondents which represents one hundred and seventy-seven (177) have BSC/HND. However, one hundred and eighty-nine (189) respondents which represent 34.3 percent either have MSC or MBA. More so, seventy-nine (79) respondent which represents 13.7% have acquires PhD. This as the one of demographic item helps us to identify the education qualification of the respondents.

4.1.4 AGE

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 18-25	313	52.4	54.2	54.2
26-33	132	22.1	22.9	77.1
34-40	31	5.2	5.4	82.5
41-50	37	6.2	6.4	88.9
51-ABOVE	64	10.7	11.1	100.0
Total	577	96.6	100.0	

Source: Field Survey 2025

Table 4.3 above depicted the age bracket of the respondents. The distribution shows that 54.2% of the respondents are between the age brackets of 18 to 25 years while 22.9% respondents are within the age bracket of 26-33 years. On the same note, 5.4% of the respondents are within the age bracket of 34 - 40 years. On the same note, 6.4% of the respondents are within the age bracket of 41 - 50 years, while the remaining respondents representing 11.1% are within the age bracket of 51 years and above.

4.1.5 Years in service

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 1-10	293	39.0	50.8	40.4
11-15	161	27.0	27.9	68.3
16-20	80	13.4	13.9	82.1
21-above	43	7.2	7.5	100.0
Total	577	96.6	100.0	

Source: Field Survey 2025

The table above indicates that two hundred and ninety-three (293) respondents which representing 50.8% percent maintain that they have been in the services for 10yres or less while 27. % Percent of the respondents which represents one hundred and sixty-one (161) have work in the local government for over 15yrs. However, eighty (80) respondents which represent 13.9 percent either have work for 16-20 years. More so, forty-three (43) respondent which represents 7.3% have work between 21-above. This as the one of demographic item helps us to identify the number of years the respondent has work for.

Hypotheses Testing

HO₁: Training has no significant relationship on economic sustainability of cosmetics retail firms in Anambra State

Correlations

	ECOS	TRA
Pearson Correlation ECOS	1.000	.538
TRA	.538	1.000
Sig. (1-tailed) ECOS	.	.000

	TRA	.000		
N	ECOS	577		577
	TRA	577		577

Sources: SPSS Output 2025

As presented in Table above there was a positive relationship between Training and economic sustainability ($r=0.538$; $p<0.05$). This suggests that, Training positively influenced sustainability of cosmetics retail firms in Anambra State. This implies that the issue of the interrelation between Training and economic sustainability is brought out clearly in this study. Therefore null hypotheses is rejected while the alternative hypotheses is affected as a result Training has significant relationship on economic sustainability of cosmetics retail firms in Anambra State

HO₂: Talent acquisition has no significant relationship on economic sustainability of cosmetics retail firms in Anambra State

Correlations

		ECOS	TRA
Pearson Correlation	ECOS	1.000	.690
	TRA	.690	1.000
Sig. (1-tailed)	ECOS	.	.000
	TRA	.000	.
N	ECOS	577	577
	TRA	577	577

Sources: SPSS Output 2025

As presented in Table above there was a positive relationship between Talent acquisition and economic sustainability ($r=0.690$; $p<0.05$). This suggests that Talent acquisition positively affect economic sustainability of cosmetics retail firms in Anambra State. This implies that the issue of the interrelation between Talent acquisition and economic sustainability is brought out clearly in this study. The study accept alternative hypotheses which states that Talent acquisition has significant relationship on economic sustainability of cosmetics retail firms in Anambra State

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The study concludes that training, Talent acquisition, Succession planning as well as Performance management has positive effect on firm sustainability and such effect is strong and statistically significant. Their coefficients are statistically different from zero at less than 5 percent level of significance. It is obvious to management that training, Talent acquisition, Succession planning as well as Performance management is sine qua non for stimulating firm sustainability in any organization. The contribution that human resource planning practices makes to an organization's performance in our present good business atmosphere is a crucial business strategy that must be employed by cosmetics firms in order to improve quality, reduce cost and enhance sustainability growth. Managing human resource planning effectively will overcome the continuing shortage of trained people as we strive to throw off the bonds of economic backwardness and seek to achieve the socio-economic objective of our national development plan. It should be noted from the result that there is a significant sub sector specific effects of various human resource planning practices. There is need to improve upon the level of investment so as to produce positive efficiency effect for productivity sustainability in the cosmetics sector in Anambra State. The study concluded that human resource planning practices has significant relationship on sustainability of cosmetics retail firms in Anambra State. The study recommendation Employees should be trained according to the present content of the environment. Therefore, seminars/ workshop should be regularly organized by the management in order to update the employee knowledge Cosmetics retail firms should ensure the protection of their talent acquired within the organization so as to gain a better employee creativity and better performance

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